

Integrating Digital Tools and Sustainable Practices for Pattachitra Painting

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Abstract:

This study explores the feasibility of using layered recycled cotton fabric samples coated with tamarind seed paste, digitally designed, and traced as a canvas for painting to integrate the traditional heritage and sustainable technological interventions. The layered sample consists of alternating layers of cotton fabric and tamarind paste, arranged as follows: a layer of cotton fabric, followed by a coating of tamarind paste, then another layer of cotton fabric, and topped with an additional layer of tamarind paste. The layered sample was oven-dried at optimized conditions for a stiff, foldable, and sheet-like structure. Motifs were created in Adobe Illustrator using digital design inspiration and then manually traced for outlining purposes. Further color fill was done using natural pigments, per the aesthetics of examples from much Indian painting heritage like Pattachitra. The study shows that utilizing digital tools and sustainable materials can enhance the preservation and promotion of Pattachitra.

Keywords: Cotton, Digital Design Development, Pattachitra, Sustainability, Tamarind Seed

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1. Introduction

Indian traditional paintings are examples of the vibrant cultural diversity of various regions nationwide. Pattachitra is a traditional style of scroll painting rooted in Odisha (formerly Orissa) and is also widely known in West Bengal [1]. In view of literal meaning, the Sanskrit term "Chitra" represents "picture," and the word "patta" represents the cloth. Usually, old, worn cotton sarees /fabrics and dried palm leaves are used as drawing canvas for these paintings. Among different categories, Pattachitra paintings commonly feature scenes from Hindu epics such as the Ramayana, Mahabharata, and legends of Lord Krishna. Traditional painting techniques include the application of tamarind seed gum and chalk powder on fabric layers, followed by sun-drying. In recent years, this intricate scroll painting has faced a notable decline; influenced by changing societal interests and economic challenges, a multifaceted decline emerged [2].

Modernization has led younger generations to stray from traditional art forms, while economic hardships and limited market access have made it increasingly difficult for artisans to sustain their craft. Moreover, the influx of mass-produced imitations has devalued authentic Pattachitra works, further threatening the livelihoods of skilled practitioners [3]. Efforts are needed to raise awareness, support, and foster appreciation for Pattachitra art to ensure its preservation for future generations [4]. Traditional painting techniques include tamarind seed gum application on fabric layers and sun-drying for three to four days.

The natural and biodegradable materials, such as cotton and

tamarind paste, align with the growing demand for sustainable practices in textile production. As a renewable and biodegradable fiber, cotton has a significantly lower environmental impact than synthetic fibers, especially when organically sourced. Organic cotton farming, which uses less water and eliminates harmful pesticides, reduces environmental degradation [5]. Tamarind paste, a plant-derived polymer, is a biodegradable and sustainable alternative to synthetic adhesives and binders, often petroleum-based. Utilizing such natural materials reduces the dependency on non-renewable resources and supports the global shift towards circular economy models in textiles [6].

The application of tamarind paste also aligns with the principles of sustainable material development, offering low toxicity and environmental impact, especially when replacing synthetic adhesives that contribute to microplastic pollution [7]. Further, using such biodegradable components ensures the end-of-life disposal of textiles has a minimal ecological footprint. Recent advancements in bio-based materials in textile processing highlight their role in reducing environmental waste and improving overall sustainability in the industry [8].

To expedite the conventional drying process, the coated layered fabric was oven-dried compared to the traditional lengthy air-drying process. This study investigates the feasibility of oven-dry optimization for recycled cotton fabric coated with tamarind seed paste as a canvas for Pattachitra painting. After drying, computer-edited motifs were printed, manually traced with precise outlining, and painted with natural pigments to offer traditional aesthetics.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this study include 100% recycled

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cotton fabric samples (plain weave) obtained from old student lab submissions and sourced from a local market. Tamarind seed pods and distilled water were also procured from the local market. Additionally, natural pigments such as ochre madder and Gum Arabic were utilized to prepare and treat the fabric samples.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Fabric Preparation coated with tamarind seed paste

Crushed tamarind seed pods were soaked overnight in an earthen pot, following traditional methods. After removing the seed coats manually, the seeds were ground into a fine powder and sieved to produce tamarind kernel powder [9,10]. A 5% w/v gel-like solution was then prepared by dissolving the powder in water [11]. This gel was carefully applied to the fabric samples using a soft brush, layer by layer, to avoid bubbles and creases, ensuring an even coating with approximately 85% paste pick-up. A second layer of cotton fabric was placed on top, followed by another application of tamarind paste. The samples were then dried in an oven at varying temperatures (50°C, 70°C, 90°C) and durations (5 min, 15 min, 25 min). The process was optimized for dimensional stability, subjective handle, and yellowness.

2.2.2 Digital Design Development

Digital mood boards were prepared in CANVA, focusing on three criteria: authenticity and respect for tradition, visual creativity, and innovation [12]. The outline drawing of Pattachitra motifs was crafted using Adobe Illustrator software, ensuring precision and detail. The designs were printed on paper and traced on an oven-dried fabric sheet at optimum conditions.

2.2.3 Preparation of natural pigment paste

Natural pigments were ground into a fine powder using a mortar and pestle. To create a smooth solution, gum Arabic powder was dissolved in warm water using a ratio of 1 part gum Arabic to 3 parts water. A small quantity of the gum Arabic paste was blended with the desired natural pigment until achieving a smooth consistency like traditional paint.

2.2.4 Painting with Natural Pigment

The prepared pigments were used to fill the outlined areas with vibrant colors characteristic of Pattachitra painting using fine brushes. The colors were layered as needed to achieve depth and intensity, following the traditional techniques and color schemes of Pattachitra art. The painting achieved an excellent depth of shade with the natural pigment paste, which will aid in repeating the trials effectively.

2.3 Testing Method

2.3.1 Dimensional Stability

Shrinkage was evaluated by measuring fabric dimensions before and after drying.

2.3.2 Subjective Assessment

Three textile experts with experience in fabric analysis were invited to assess the surface handle and morphology of coated fabrics. The experts examined samples under controlled lighting and magnification conditions, evaluating the surface morphology for uniformity, smoothness, defects (such as cracks or bubbles), handle, and color variation.

3. Results and Discussion

The study includes three stages: optimization of oven-drying conditions, Digital design development for outline tracing, and final product development based on the Pattachitra theme.

3.1 Optimisation of Oven-drying conditions for fabric samples coated with tamarind seed paste

The tamarind seed paste-coated fabric samples were processed according to specific temperature and time conditions, as detailed in Table 1. After drying, the samples were evaluated based on critical parameters, including dimensional stability, subjective handle, color variation, and surface morphology, as outlined in Table 1.

3.1.1 Dimensional Stability

Minimal shrinkage was observed at lower drying temperatures, with significant shrinkage (up to 3%) recorded at 90°C. This shrinkage is attributed to the combined effects of moisture loss and thermal contraction of the tamarind seed paste and the cotton fibers. Higher temperatures lead to moisture evaporation from the paste and fabric, causing the cotton fibers to contract and resulting in dimensional reduction [13, 14]. Such thermal effects are more pronounced at elevated temperatures due to the nature of the cotton fibers, which tend to shrink when exposed to prolonged heat.

3.1.2 Subjective Assessment

The coated fabrics were also assessed subjectively for key properties like handle and flexibility, as described in the testing methods. At lower drying temperatures, the samples exhibited excellent softness and foldability. However, as drying temperatures increased, the fabrics became progressively stiffer. Optimal hand feel was achieved at 90°C for 15 minutes, balancing stiffness and softness, making the fabric suitable for forming three-dimensional structures [15]. Conversely, at longer drying times, such as 25 minutes, the tamarind coating became brittle and less pliable, negatively impacting foldability. Shorter drying times (5 minutes) retained excessive softness, which was undesirable for the intended application as a sheet-like material for coating [16].

Table 1: Properties of tamarind seed-coated cotton fabric layers for different drying conditions

Run No.	Temperature and Time	Dimensional Stability	Subjective Assessment		
			Handle	Colour Variation	Surface Morphology
1	50°C for 5 min	No Shrinkage	Soft and foldable	No discoloration	Uneven, sticky, and tacky coating
2	50°C for 15 min	No Shrinkage	Stiff and foldable	No discoloration	Sticky coating
3	50°C for 25 min	Shrinkage (1%) & wrinkles	Stiff, not foldable	Mild discoloration	Cracks in coating
4	70°C for 5 min	No Shrinkage	Soft and foldable	No discoloration	Uneven, sticky, and tacky coating
5	70°C for 15 min	No Shrinkage	Stiff and foldable	No discoloration	Uniform coating
6	70°C for 25 min	Shrinkage (1%) & wrinkles	Stiff, not foldable	Mild discoloration	Cracks in coating
7	90°C for 5 min	No Shrinkage	Soft and foldable	No discoloration	Uneven, sticky, and tacky coating
8	90°C for 15 min	Shrinkage (3%) & wrinkles	Soft and foldable	Mild discoloration	Cracks in coating
9	90°C for 25 min	Shrinkage (3%) & wrinkles	Stiff, not foldable	Paleness	Cracks in coating

Color Variation

A mild discoloration of the fabric was noted after 25 minutes of drying, particularly at higher temperatures. At 90°C, a trend toward paleness was observed (Runs 8 and 9). This color change is likely due to the thermal degradation of the tamarind seed paste, which can affect the appearance of the coated fabric [17]. Prolonged exposure to high temperatures can cause pigmentation changes, potentially altering the aesthetic qualities of the finished fabric.

Surface Morphology

At shorter drying times (5 minutes), a tacky and uneven surface was observed across all temperature ranges. This

suggests that the tamarind paste had not fully solidified or bonded to the cotton fibers. Inadequate temperature or drying time may result in incomplete moisture removal, creating a sticky surface that could lead to adhesion problems and transfer of the coating onto other surfaces [18]. At longer drying times (25 minutes), especially at higher temperatures, cracks were visible in the paste coating, reducing the coated fabric's visual appeal and functional properties. The best results were obtained in Run 5 (70°C for 15 minutes), which produced a uniform, non-tacky surface with no discoloration or shrinkage while maintaining a firm but foldable texture [19]. This optimized condition was then used to create a foldable lamp structure, as shown in Figure 1(i).

Figure 1: Steps involved in the development of folded structure made of tamarind seed-coated oven-dried layered cotton

3.2 Digital design development for outline drawing and tracing

The next significant phase of the research involves creating intricate digital representations of patterns or designs for outline sketching and tracing, which are then meant to be translated into stiff cotton fabric sheets.

3.2.1 Designing of different mood- boards for motif and colour-combination

Two mood boards were created for sampling: a traditional mood board and a contemporary one. The moodboard elements included patterns, motifs, color schemes, materials, and techniques. Images from various art galleries, official websites, social media, etc., were used to create mood boards. The mood boards are shown on the following pages in Figure 2 [20-24].

Figure 2: Mood Board for Traditional and Contemporary Themes

3.2.2 Selection of mood-board for the further designing

Two different groups evaluated the above-designed mood boards: Students and teachers from Textile and Apparel Technology, who were aware of traditional Pattachitra art, make up Group A. Group B consisted of Computer Engineering students and faculty members who may not have technical knowledge of textile design but who do have a sense of aesthetics, especially when it comes to traditional art forms. They provided insightful preference ratings despite little understanding of the design's intricacy. (Table 2)

For two elements—patterns and motifs, as well as color palette focus—a difference in ratings was observed between Group A and Group B. Respondents in Group A preferred the preservation and continuation of cultural heritage, which motivated the use of traditional motifs for the final design development. However, contemporary interpretations of Pattachitra were accepted by consumers who were not strictly aligned with traditional integrity.

In contrast, both groups showed a keen acceptance of new and innovative technologies for materials and technique options. It agrees with the perception of another study that suggested opportunities for incorporating many traditional Indian art styles into modern new media applications [25, 26]. This result further motivated the implementation of digital design methodologies in the next stage. Moreover,

traditional elements were equally rated by Group B respondents, indicating agreement with the research objective of adapting traditional art to new trends while maintaining the artistic integrity and historical significance of Pattachitra. As shown in Table 2, the traditional mood board received higher preference ratings and has been finalized for the next design steps.

Table 2: Results of preference rating (average) for two mood-boards

Mood board Elements	Focus	Group-A	Group-B
Traditional			
Patterns and Motifs	Mythological	4.5	4.4
Color Palette	Traditional colors and natural dyes	4.3	4.2
Materials	Mostly traditional	4.25	4.0
Techniques	Traditional techniques	4.5	4.4
AVERAGE RATING		4.38	4.25
Contemporary			
Patterns and Motifs	Creative over traditional elements	2.8	3.5
Color Palette	Vibrant colors	2.8	3.5
Materials	Modern materials	4.0	4.0

3.3 Final Product Development

Students were motivated by the drawings related to Lord Krishna and the Ganjifa cards theme. As shown in Figure 3, drawing elements were repeated and edited in size, etc. (shown with arrows in Figure 3(a), Figure 4(a)). Using graphic software allowed creative combinations for precise

Figure 3: Steps involved in the development of lamp from painted cotton sheets at optimised conditions

Figure 4: Steps involved in the development of card from painted cotton sheets at optimized conditions

and intricate design creation. This precision can enhance the overall quality and aesthetic appeal of Pattachitra artworks. Before finalizing the artwork, students digitally tried various design elements, color combinations, and compositions. This flexibility encouraged creative exploration without the risk of wasting materials. Hence, virtual prototypes may help finalize the design with reduced wastage for sample preparation. Traced samples were then painted for inside filling using natural pigment printing pastes for different colors.

As shown in the figure, the final design was traced on a processed oven-dried coated cotton fabric sheet, and the color was filled and folded to give the shape of a lamp (Figure3).

Similarly, Card samples were prepared; here again, the outline design was prepared in CAD, printed, and finished in the form of cards. (Figure 4)

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4. Conclusion

Recycled cotton fabric layers were coated with tamarind seed paste as per the traditional design heritage of Pattchitra paintings. To speed up the process, coated fabric samples were oven-dried and optimized with respect to drying temperature and time. Optimal drying conditions were identified as 70°C for 15 minutes, ensuring effective dimensional stability, surface morphology, and minimum minutes, ensuring effective dimensional stability, surface morphology, and minimum color variation conducive to natural pigment paintings. Motifs designed in Adobe Illustrator were used for outline tracing, followed by natural pigment color fill and folded product samples. Utilizing recycled lab samples promotes sustainability by reducing waste and conserving resources. These findings support the development of sustainable and innovative oven drying methods followed by digital design techniques and natural painting techniques for faster sampling of cotton fabric-based Pattachitra paintings.

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